

Critical Experiment under Under-Moderation Conditions with an Iron-Loaded Core Using the Modified STACY

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ABSTRACT

To contribute to criticality safety control of fuel debris generated during the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant accident, the Japan Atomic Energy Agency (JAEA) has been conducting critical experiments using the modified Static Experiment Critical Facility (STACY) with compositions simulating fuel debris. These experiments aim to provide benchmark data for validating nuclear data libraries and computational methods under conditions relevant to fuel debris.

The objective of this study is to obtain critical experimental data under under-moderated conditions. The experimental cores of the modified STACY were composed of light water, UO₂ fuel rods. To reproduce such conditions while considering the constraint on the available number of fuel rods, a two-region core configuration consisting of a driver region and a test region, was employed in the modified STACY. The test region with a 1.27-cm lattice pitch is surrounded by the driver region, in which fuel rods are arranged in a checkerboard pattern on a 1.27-cm lattice plate, with a 1.80-cm lattice pitch. In addition, samples simulating iron, one of the major structural materials expected in fuel debris, were loaded into the core to evaluate its influence on criticality under the under-moderation conditions.

Numerical analyses were performed using the MVP-3 code with JENDL-4.0 and JENDL-5 nuclear data libraries. The calculations using JENDL-5 demonstrated that the bias between experimental and calculated results tends to decrease under under-moderated conditions compared to optimal moderation conditions.

Keywords: STACY, Critical experiment, Fuel debris, Stainless Steel, Two-region core

1. INTRODUCTION

The criticality safety control of fuel debris generated during the Tokyo Electric Power Company's Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Plant accident is one of the most crucial issues for the safety retrieval of the fuel debris. It is considered that fuel debris is formed through various processes such as molten core concrete interactions, and nuclear fuel was mixed with the reactor structural materials such as iron and concrete. The investigation of the criticality characteristics of mixture of the fuel and structural materials is necessary for the criticality control.

Computation analyses have been performed in simulating various compositions [1-3]. To validate the computation analyses, the first experimental campaign was conducted under optimum moderation conditions in the modified STACY [4-6]. However, experiments under under-moderated conditions had not been conducted due to time constraints and the limited number of available fuel rods. Therefore, in this study, new experiments were conducted, and a two-region core configuration was employed to

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reproduce under-moderated conditions within the constraint of the available fuel rods [7]. Using this approach, new experimental data under under-moderated conditions were successfully obtained.

In this study, to investigate the effect of iron under under-moderation conditions, experimental devices referred to as “steel rods,” which simulate iron components, were loaded into the test region of the two-region core. Critical experiments were performed for three different core configurations. The experimental results were analyzed with calculations performed using a continuous-energy Monte Carlo code MVP [8], employing both JENDL-4.0 [9] and JENDL-5 [10] nuclear data libraries.

2. EXPERIMENT

The overview of the modified STACY is shown in Fig. 1. The core of the modified STACY is composed of light water moderator in an open-top core tank 180-cm in diameter and 190-cm high, and fuel rods loaded on a base plate and three grid plates.

Each of the fuel rods are 9.5-mm in diameter and 1495-mm high and consist of UO₂ pellets, which is 8.19-mm in diameter, with 4.98wt.% ²³⁵U enrichment and zircaloy cladding. The base plate and the three grid plates are made of aluminum alloy (A6061), and the thickness of base plate and grid plates are 20-mm and 12-mm, respectively.

Guide pins made of zircaloy are also loaded in the core tank to insert safety plates. The steel rods were manufactured from Type 304 stainless steel (18% Cr, 8% Ni) to prevent corrosion. They have the same diameter as the fuel rods and can be loaded into the same positions as the fuel rods within the core.

Figure 1. Overview of the modified STACY.

The core configurations are listed on Table I and Cross section view of these cores are shown in Fig. 2. The test region, with a lattice pitch of 12.7 mm, had dimensions of either 15 × 15 or 17 × 17. This region was surrounded by the driver region. The fuel rods in the driver region were loaded in a checkerboard pattern, whose interval is 18.0-mm (12.7 × 2^{1/2}-mm). The number of fuel rods in the driver region was adjusted to achieve a critical water level between 70 cm and 100 cm. The steel rods were loaded from the center of the core to the outside while preserving the symmetry of the loading position.

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The modified STACY is not equipped with control rods; therefore, reactivity is controlled by adjusting the water level in the core tank. The water level was measured using a servo-type level gauge, with the bottom of the fuel pellet defined as the reference (zero) point.

Measured critical level data were also listed in Table I. Criticality was determined after the water level was adjusted by the operator once the system exceeded criticality and the reactor power was confirmed to be stable. The critical water levels are reported as the indications of the level gauge, and the measurement accuracy is estimated to be ± 1.5 mm based on the pre-service inspection [11].

Table I. Experimental cores and measured critical water level data.

RUN	MAP	# of Steel rod	Temperature[°C]	Water Level [mm]
R803	1-S25-1-348	25	19.2	915.5
R804	1-S25-1-348	25	20.1	915.3
R805	1-S25-1-348	25	19.1	916.3
R806	1-S49-1-392	49	19.4	853.3
R811	1-S09-3-348	9	20.0	766.2

Figure 2. Cross section views of the core configurations.

3. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

In the experimental analysis, as shown in Fig. 3, the fuel rods, the three grid plates, and the base plate were modeled, while the complex internal structures of the core tank and the detailed structure of the end cup of the fuel rod were neglected.

The core tank temperature is measured at two locations near the bottom of the tank. In this analysis, the temperature distribution within the core was not considered, and the tank temperature was assumed to be uniform throughout the core region. The change in water volume as a function of temperature was evaluated using the equation reported by Kell [12].

The calculations were performed by a general-purpose Monte Carlo code for Neutron and Photon Transport Calculations Based on Continuous Energy MVP-3 [8] with the nuclear libraries of JENDL-4.0 [9] and JENDL-5 [10]. The number of histories was set so that the Monte Carlo uncertainty of the effective multiplication factor was less than 10pcm.

Figure 3. Calculation model of the modified STACY.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental data in under-moderation condition and optimum-moderation condition [5] were compared with the calculations using JENDL-4.0 and JENDL-5 as shown in Figure 4. A clear trend observed in the results is that the calculations using JENDL-5, indicated by blue markers, exhibit larger biases compared to those using JENDL-4.0, shown in red markers. This tendency is consistent with previous JENDL-5 benchmark studies [13] and has also been confirmed in other STACY experiments [14]. The primary factors contributing to this difference are considered to include updates to the thermal scattering law (TSL) for hydrogen and revisions to the cross sections of O-16, U-235, and U-238.

In addition, a characteristic trend specific to the present experimental configuration is the relationship with the amount of steel rods loaded into the core. Similar to optimum-moderation conditions [5], the discrepancies between experimental and calculated results increase as the number of steel rods increases; this tendency was also observed under-moderation conditions. Furthermore, the dependency on the number of loaded rods is more pronounced for JENDL-5 than for JENDL-4.0. This may be attributed to modifications in the cross sections of nuclei contained in the steel rods, suggesting the need for detailed sensitivity analyses to identify the most influential nuclides.

When comparing the results for under- and optimum-moderation conditions using JENDL-5, the biases are smaller under under-moderated conditions. This difference may be attributed not only to variations in neutron spectra, which could provide insights into the influence of thermal neutron scattering laws for iron, but also to the characteristics of the two-region core configuration adopted in this study. In particular, the reactivity worth, and thus the importance, of the test region is inherently lower under under moderation conditions than under optimum moderation, reducing its contribution to the overall core effective multiplication factor and diminishing the magnitude of observable biases. Therefore, future work will include detailed analyses of iron TSL effects, neutron spectra, and reaction rates, along with additional examinations of importance effects to better understand the influence of the two-region core.

configuration.

Figure 4. Comparison the experimental data in optimum moderation (white outline) and undermoderation conditions with the calculation results performed by MVP-3 with JENDL-4.0 (red) and JENDL-5 (blue).

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, critical experiments were conducted using the modified STACY to obtain data under under-moderation conditions, which had not been previously investigated due to experimental constraints. A two-region core configuration was employed with 12.7-cm lattice plates to reproduce under-moderation conditions, enabling the evaluation of the impact of iron components on core reactivity.

The obtained experimental data were compared with calculation results using the MVP-3 code with JENDL-4.0 and JENDL-5 nuclear data libraries. It was confirmed that, similar to optimal moderation conditions, the discrepancy between experimental and calculated results tends to increase with the amount of steel rods loaded into the core under under-moderation conditions. Notably, while JENDL-4.0 showed consistent bias trends across both moderation conditions, JENDL-5 exhibited smaller biases under under-moderation conditions compared to optimal moderation, indicating improved performance in such systems.

To further understand the cause of these differences, future work will focus on detailed investigations of neutron spectra, reaction rates, and sensitivity analyses. These studies will help clarify the influence of elemental composition within the steel rods and the potential impact of the driver region introduced by the two-region core configuration.

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